

Unified Theory of Diffraction and the Theory of Liquids

Part I. Generalized Partition Function for Matter of Any Kind¹.

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Statistical mechanical theories of crystalline and gaseous states are quite well established, but that of the liquid state is still far from satisfactory. Nevertheless, the approach to the liquid state from the standpoint of crystalline arrangements has been more successful than that from the gaseous state. This is not surprising in view of the well known fact that many properties of crystalline and liquid states are very close to one another. In this note, assuming the existence of distorted lattices in matter, a generalized expression for the partition function (pf) of matter of *any kind* and that of the liquid state in particular has been derived.

Matter is usually classified into crystals, liquids and amorphous substances (or gases) according to the nature of their diffraction patterns. The unified theory of diffraction² has proved that from the standpoint of the diffraction theory the difference between crystals, liquids and gaseous (or amorphous) states lies in the degree of distortion of a lattice. Let us then consider an infinitely large ideal crystal at 0°K. Due to anharmonic vibrations of the atoms (or molecules) lattice distortions will appear with increasing temperatures. As a result in addition to the vibrations of the atoms around their mean positions, the lattice vectors themselves (defined as the mean position around which the atoms vibrate) will change randomly both in their directions and in their magnitudes. Let $H_p(\vec{x})$ denote the normalized frequency of distribution for the location of the centroid of the p th atom whose coordinates in terms of the fundamental vectors of the first neighbours are (p_1, p_2, p_3) . Then

$$H_p(\vec{x}) = (H_{100}^* H_{100}^{* * * *})^{|\vec{p}_1| - 1} (H_{100}^* H_{010}^{* * * *})^{|\vec{p}_2| - 1} (H_{010}^* H_{001}^{* * * *})^{|\vec{p}_3| - 1} H_{001} \quad (1)$$

(* symbol for the convolution product)

where $H_{100}(\vec{x})$, $H_{010}(\vec{x})$, $H_{001}(\vec{x})$ represent the distribution functions of these fundamental vectors. As shown previously (see ref. 2 Chs. II, IV and IX) this is exactly true if the fundamental vectors can vary independently and is a very good approximation for the general case. Hence knowing the three distribution functions of the fundamental vectors one can calculate the distribution function for the location of the centroid of the p th atom.

1. Work supported by the National Research Council of Canada.
2. R. Hosemann and S. N. Bagchi. *Direct Analysis of Diffraction by Matter*. North Holland Pub. Co., Amsterdam, 1962.
3. S. N. Bagchi, *this journal*, 1969, **46**, 376.

Now, let us assume that an infinitely large crystal lattice breaks down into M clusters of distorted lattices and each distorted lattice contains N atoms (or molecules) and the system of clusters behave as "perfect giant molecules", the partition function of the entire system can be written as

$$Z = \frac{[z_{cl}^{cl}]^M}{M!} \cdot (z_{cl})^M ; z_{cl} = Q_N(V, T) \cdot z_{vib} \quad (2)$$

where z_{cl}^{cl} is the classical pf of each distorted lattice due to the translational energy and z_{cl} is the internal pf for each distorted lattice. z_{vib} represents the pf in each distorted lattice due to the vibration of the atoms around their mean lattice positions, and can be calculated, for example, from Debye's theory of specific heats. The only unknown quantity in (2) to be evaluated is $Q_N(V, T)$. If the number of particles in the distorted lattice is sufficiently large so that we can neglect the boundary effects, then the potential energy of any particular atom due to all other atoms is on the average the same as of any other atom. Consequently, assuming the superposition principle, we can write

$$Q_N(V, T) = \exp\left[-\beta/2 \cdot \sum_p \phi_p\right] = \pi Q_p$$

$$Q_p = \iiint \exp\left[-\beta/2 \cdot \phi(\mathbf{x})\right] \cdot H_p(\mathbf{x}) d\mathbf{v} \quad (3)$$

$\beta = 1/kT$, $\phi(\mathbf{x})$ is the potential energy between a pair of atoms at a relative distance \mathbf{x} . The expression (3) is to be evaluated for all possible values of p . An adequate expression for many purposes is

$$Q_N(V, T) \approx \exp(-\beta N \bar{\psi}) \quad (4)$$

where the average potential energy of an atom is given by

$$\bar{\psi} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_p \iiint \phi(\mathbf{x}) \cdot H_p(\mathbf{x}) d\mathbf{v} \quad (5)$$

The functions $H_{100}(\mathbf{x})$, $H_{010}(\mathbf{x})$, $H_{001}(\mathbf{x})$ can in principle be determined from X-ray data. Consequently, choosing a suitable $\phi(\mathbf{x})$ one can calculate the pf of any substance.

In the case of simple liquids, the distribution function of each atom in relation to its own neighbours is statistically the same and consequently eq. (1) is valid for all such systems. Further in such cases only one function, namely,

$$H_1(r) = \frac{1}{(\pi\alpha^2)^{3/2}} \exp\left[-r^2/\alpha^2\right] \quad (6)$$

properly shifted would give rise not only to

$$H_{100}(\mathbf{x}), H_{010}(\mathbf{x}), H_{001}(\mathbf{x}) \text{ but also to any } H_p(\mathbf{x})$$

if we use (1). The spherically symmetrical distribution function for the n th neighbour is then given by³ $\sum_p H_p(r)$,

* p^{th} atom is supposed to be the n^{th} neighbour.

where
$$H_p(r) = \frac{1}{4r_0\pi^{3/2}\Delta} \cdot \frac{1}{r} \cdot \left\{ \exp - \left[\frac{(r-r_p)}{\Delta} \right]^2 - \exp - \left[\frac{(r+r_p)}{\Delta} \right]^2 \right\} \quad (7)$$

$\Delta^2 = m\alpha^2$; m = the number of convolutions of independent fundamental vectors to reach the point p .

p represents the p th atom whose coordinates are (p_1, p_2, p_3) in terms of the fundamental vectors of the neighbours and (q_1, q_2, q_3) in terms of the fundamental crystal lattice vectors $\mathbf{a}_1, \mathbf{a}_2, \mathbf{a}_3$ at 0°K . The summation over p is to be extended for all the atoms which lie at the same radial distance

$$r_0 = |q_1 \mathbf{a}_1 + q_2 \mathbf{a}_2 + q_3 \mathbf{a}_3| \quad (8)$$

(for all possible values of q_1, q_2, q_3)

It might be noted that neither $H_p(r)$ nor the spherically symmetrical distribution function for the n th neighbour $H_n(r)$ are Gaussian functions.

Thus for the case of simple liquids the configuration integral $Q_N(V, T)$ in (3) is reduced to

$$Q_N(V, T) = \prod_p Q_p$$

$$Q_p = \iiint \exp -[\beta/2 \cdot \phi(r)] \cdot H_p(r) dv \quad (9)$$

A simpler (but adequate for most purposes) expression for the pf is obtained by calculating first the average potential energy of an atom

$$\bar{\psi} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_p \iiint \phi(r) \cdot H_p(r) dv \quad (10)$$

and then using (4).

Results of calculations for the pf and the thermodynamic properties of simple liquids based on (9) and the new analysis of RDF will be reported later on.

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